

CP52: MtrunA17_Chr3g0100221

CP54: MtrunA17_Chr3g0105981

CP57: MtrunA17_Chr3g0124631

CP59: MtrunA17_Chr3g0130671

CP60: MtrunA17_Chr3g0135761

CP61: MtrunA17_Chr3g0137391

CP62: MtrunA17_Chr3g0141901

-1 (2a2→1a1)

CP84: MtrunA17_Chr5g0408581

CP94: MtrunA17_Chr5g0444231

CP98: MtrunA17_Chr6g0457461

-2 (2r→3a)

Supplementary Dataset S7 Part 2. A graphical summary on folding predictions for MS-supported chimeric peptide models (CPs) 51-100. The rest of the legend is the same as for Supplementary Dataset S7 Part 1.